

GIANTLEAP

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Validation of degradation mechanisms and diagnostics in demonstration

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Abstract: The objective of this task was to validate the models of degradation mechanisms early developed against data from experiments and demonstration, in particular by quantifying the time scale of accelerated testing protocols against long-term degradation data. This was possible by comparing the results from the 2000 hours stack run at EK with the degradation rates observed during the accelerated stress tests at FESB. An equivalent of 0.75 to 1.23 cycles in the accelerated stress test to one hour of stack operating time has been obtained, depending whether the cell was allowed rejuvenation or not. Unfortunately, because of unsteady operating conditions and because of the short duration of stacks operation at the test bench and in the trailer, it was not possible to detect any degradation patterns in order to compare them to the results from the accelerated stress tests. Previously proposed and developed method for single measurement of low frequency impedance intercept was first tested on full stack at EK and then incorporated in the trailer as a predictive function of the control unit. During the commissioning and trial runs of the trailer, an attempt was made to measure low frequency impedance.

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1 Objectives

The objective of this task was to validate the models of degradation mechanisms developed in D1.4 against data from experiments and demonstration, in particular by quantifying the time scale of accelerated testing protocols against long-term degradation data.

2 Available stack data from experiments and demonstration

For this deliverable, analysis has been performed on the available data provided by ElringKlinger (EK) and Bosch Engineering (BEG):

- EK test-bench polarization curves of the fuel cell stack before and after durability testing (1 XLSX file):
 - DataFCLab_TST7_0-2250h_submitted
- EK test-bench polarization curves of the fuel cell stack at atmospheric and pressurized operation (1 XLSX file):
 - GIANTLEAP_Stacks_TestbenchOperation_EK
- BEG test-bench data during the first firing and commissioning of the stacks within the complete fuel cell system (26 CSV files):
 - 2017-07-17_12-55_TestBench_PoleCurve_Atmospheric_01
 - 2017-07-17_17-01_TestBench_PoleCurve_Atmospheric_02
 - 2017-07-20_14-42_TestBench_PoleCurve_atmospheric
 - 2017-07-24_16-56_TestBench_70kW_1500mbar
 - 2017-07-25_12-48_TestBench_PoleCurve_1600mbar_01
 - 2017-07-25_16-40_TestBench_PoleCurve_1600mbar_02
 - 2017-07-25_17-51_TestBench_PoleCurve_1500mbar_01
 - 2017-07-26_14-17_TestBench_74kW_1800mbar_01
 - 2017-07-27_15-05_TestBench_65kW_1800mbar_01
 - 2017-07-27_15-45_TestBench_60kW_PressureVariation_01
 - 2017-08-01_16-49_TestBench_55kW_1600mbar_01
 - 2017-08-07_15-22_TestBench_65kW_1700mbar_01
 - 2018-01-29_16-21_TestBench_PowerVariation_WarmUp_01
 - 2018-01-29_17-06_TestBench_PowerVariation_02
 - 2018-01-30_18-55_TestBench_PowerVariation_WarmUp_01
 - 2018-03-16_12-18_TestBench_PowerVariation_WarmUp_01
 - 2018-03-16_14-11_TestBench_PowerVariation_WarmUp_02
 - 2018-03-16_16-54_TestBench_55kW_atmospheric_03
 - 2018-03-16_17-16_TestBench_55kW_atmospheric_04
 - 2018-03-16_17-46_TestBench_55kW_atmospheric_05
 - 2018-07-10_18-21_TestBench_PowerVariation_06
 - 2018-07-23_16-03_TestBench_65kW_1700mbar_01
 - 2018-07-23_16-27_TestBench_50kW_1300mbar_01
 - 2018-07-23_17-59_TestBench_PowerCycles_01
 - 2018-07-25_18-57_TestBench_65kW_50kW_01
 - 2018-07-25_20-22_TestBench_PowerCycles_01
- BEG vehicle data from operation in VDL range-extender bus trailer (16 CSV files):
 - 2019-08-22_11-09_DriveRecorder_45kW_mid-p-9bar_01
 - 2019-08-22_13-11_DriveRecorder_45kW_WarmUp_mid-p-9bar
 - 2019-08-23_12-59_DriveRecorder_45kW_mid-p-9bar_01
 - 2019-08-23_13-37_DriveRecorder_45kW_mid-p-9bar_02
 - 2019-08-26_10-39_DriveRecorder_45kW_mid-p-9bar_WarmUp_01
 - 2019-08-27_14-54_DriveRecorder_45kW_mid-p-9bar_01
 - 2019-08-28_10-29_DriveRecorder_45kW_25kW_mid-p-9bar_01
 - 2019-08-29_16-34_DriveRecorder_45kW_25kW_mid-p-9bar_01
 - 2019-09-05_11-13_DriveRecorder_25kW_mid-p-9bar_WarmUp_01
 - 2019-09-05_12-03_DriveRecorder_45kW_mid-p-9bar_02
 - 2019-09-05_13-42_DriveRecorder_45kW_mid-p-9bar_03
 - 2019-10-02_12-55_DriveRecorder_65kW_25kW_01
 - 2019-10-04_09-52_DriveRecorder_65kW_WarmUp_01
 - 2019-10-04_12-59_DriveRecorder_65kW_01
 - 2019-10-30_12-18_Calibration_PolCurve_Dwn_04
 - 2019-10-30_16-53_Calibration_PolCurve_Up_05

3 Comparison of the stack data from experiments and demonstration

3.1 Analysis of the available EK test-bench data

From the available data of the stack durability testing, provided by ElringKlinger (EK), performance degradation could be clearly seen (especially at higher currents) from the comparison of the stack performance obtained after 250 h of the operation (gray curve) vs. stack performance after 2250 h (black curve) in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Stack performance comparison during 2000 h of the operation at coolant inlet temperature of 73 °C, cathode stoichiometry of 1.7 and atmospheric pressure.

FESB compared the degradation rates from the 2000 hours run of the full-size stack at EK with those obtained on a single cell exposed to an accelerated stress test (AST), as an attempt to quantify the time scale of accelerated tests results against long-term degradation data. From these curves in Figure 1, it is possible to extract the degradation rates and then compare them with the degradation rates observed during the accelerated stress tests at FESB reported in deliverable D1.4 (Figure 2). The results are shown in Table 1. This simplified analysis quantifies the time scale of accelerated tests results against long-term degradation data – between 0.75 and 1.23 cycles in the accelerated stress test correspond to one hour of stack operating time, depending whether the cell was allowed rejuvenation.

Figure 2: Comparison of the degradation rates during the accelerated stress tests on single cell at FESB (left) and stack durability testing at EK (right).

Table 1: Degradation rates during the accelerated stress tests on single cell at FESB and stack durability testing at EK.

A/cm ²	2500 hrs run		5000 cycles no rejuvenation			10000 cycles with rejuvenation		
	ΔV (V)	$\mu V/hr$	ΔV (V)	$\mu V/cycle$	cycle/hr	ΔV (V)	$\mu V/cycle$	cycle/hr
0.4	0.004	2.0	0.0187	3.74	0.53	0.0241	2.41	0.83
0.8	0.010	5.0	0.0298	5.96	0.84	0.0369	3.69	1.36
1.2	0.016	8.0	0.0449	8.97	0.89	0.0537	5.37	1.49
				Average	0.75		Average	1.23

This obtained cycle-time equivalence should be used cautiously because it has correlated two independent tests, namely a single cell exposed to external voltage cycling and a full-size stack run continuously with cycling load. The only common denominator is the membrane-electrode assembly, i.e., the catalyst layer which degraded.

From the available EK test-bench data, polarization curves of the 200-cell stack at atmospheric (light blue curve) and pressurized operation (dark blue curve) are shown in Figure 3, compared with previously given polarization curves from the stack durability testing (gray and black curves, Figure 1).

Figure 3: Performance comparison of the 200-cell stack at coolant inlet temperature of 73 °C, cathode stoichiometry of 1.7 and different pressure levels (atmospheric and 1.8 bar) vs. polarization curves measured during 2000 h of the operation within the durability testing.

As it could be seen from Figure 3, polarization curve of 200-cell stack at atmospheric pressure (light blue curve) is comparable with previously given polarization curves from the stack durability testing (gray and black curves). A slight performance differences below 150 A could be explained by the different test-bench set-ups the stacks were operated on (one for measuring degradation, the other for analysing the stack performance and sensitivity). As it could be expected, stack performance on higher pressure (1.8 bar, dark blue curve) is significantly better than the performance at atmospheric pressure (light blue curve).

3.2 Analysis of the available BEG test-bench data

In order to compare the stack performance from experiments at EK test-bench and BEG test-bench from the first firing and commissioning of the stacks within the complete fuel cell system, obtained polarization curves at different pressure levels are given in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Performance comparison of the stacks at different pressure levels and between EK and BEG test-bench operation.

As it could be seen from Figure 4, the polarization curve from the first firing on BEG test-bench (red curve) is almost the same as the polarization curve of stack (light blue) from EK test-bench, which was expected due to almost the same operating conditions (atmospheric pressure and stack temperature around 73 °C) and the same generation of the stack. Similarly, polarization curve from the commissioning of the stacks within the complete fuel cell system on BEG test-bench (purple curve) is also in accordance with these two curves (red and light blue), as it was also at the same operating conditions. However, cathode stoichiometry on BEG test-bench was generally higher compared with the cathode stoichiometry of 1.7 on EK test-bench (Figure 5), which has affected the performance especially at higher currents.

As already shown in deliverable D6.3, the cathode pressure in the system, even with membrane humidifier and muffler attached, was slightly lower than the values on the stack test bench. The cathode stoichiometry values as measured with the FCCU air flow meter however were higher, which explains the higher power output. For pressurized operation, the power output generated by the system was slightly less than the reference values and with a turbo compressor attached, the reference cathode pressure can only be reached with a minimum airflow to avoid surging. Therefore, during the measurements, the cathode air pressure was below the reference value given by the stack test bench for the lower current values, which has led to a lower power output. Moreover, an additional explanation for a slight difference visible at lower currents (below 70 A), could be also found in Figure 6, where is visible that stack was warming up during the rise of currents until 120 A (from 50 °C to over

70 °C). Through the whole measurement of the polarization curve at first firing on BEG test-bench, the stack was slightly above temperature of 70 °C, except during the measurements at lower currents when was slightly below 70 °C (Figure 7).

Figure 5: Comparison of cathode stoichiometries at test-bench and system operation [adopted from deliverable D6.3].

Figure 6: Change of stack operating conditions during the polarization curve measurement "BEG_Test-Bench_Commissioning_atm".

Figure 7: Change of stack operating conditions during the polarization curve measurement "BEG_Test-Bench_FirstFiring_atm"

From Figure 4, there is also visible improvement of the performance on higher pressures during the commissioning phase at BEG test-bench (light and dark tan curves). However, polarization curve from the commissioning on BEG test-bench at 1.5 bar (light tan curve) has a lower performance at lower currents (below 70 A) than the polarization curve from the commissioning on BEG test-bench at atmospheric pressure (purple curve). This could be explained with the rise up of the pressure (from atmospheric up to 1.5 bar) and temperature (from 55 °C to above 70 °C) during the rise of current (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Change of stack operating conditions during the polarization curve measurement "BEG_Test-Bench_Commissioning_up to 1.5 bar".

On the other side, polarization curve from the commissioning on BEG test-bench at 1.8 bar (dark tan curve in Figure 4) only performs better than the curve at 1.5 bar (light tan curve) above 200 A. This could be explained with the slow rise of the pressure (from atmospheric up to 1.8 bar) and temperature (from 63 to 73 °C) during the measurement (Figure 9), where it could be seen that pressure is around 1.8 bar and temperature is around 73 °C only above 200 A. Therefore, this part of curve is also in accordance with the polarization curve from EK test-bench at 1.8 bar (dark blue curve in Figure 4), as they are finally at the same conditions.

Figure 9: Change of stack operating conditions during the polarization curve measurement "BEG_Test-Bench_Commissioning_up to 1.8 bar".

3.3 Analysis of the available demonstration vehicle data

In order to compare the stack data from experiments with data from demonstration in range-extender bus trailer, the only available polarization curve from the vehicle (orange curve) is added for comparison in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Performance comparison of the stacks at different pressure levels between EK and BEG test-bench operation and vehicle operation in range-extender bus trailer.

From Figure 10, it is visible that polarization curve from the vehicle (orange curve) is in the best accordance with the polarization curve from the commissioning on BEG test-bench at 1.5 bar, which could be expected as they are in very comparable conditions (Figure 11 vs Figure 8).

Figure 11: Change of stack operating conditions during the polarization curve measurement "BEG Vehicle_up to 1.5 bar".

Further comparison with vehicle operation data in range-extender bus trailer could not be given, as it was not possible to measure it in demonstration for such a long period of operation. However, from the performed analysis of the available data from Bosch Engineering (BEG) test-bench operation and vehicle operation in range-extender bus trailer, comparison of few available operating points during the operating time on different days, as representatives from several days of diagnostic recordings at test-bench and trailer demonstration, is given in the Figure 12.

Figure 12: Comparison of average cell voltage vs. time for different operating points of the stack in BEG test-bench operation and vehicle operation in range-extender bus trailer (operating currents, pressures, temperatures, recording time duration and datum are given in the legend, respectively).

A higher voltage variations of the points 188 A and 245 A at BEG test-bench (blue and red curves) could be explained with older EK stack generation, as it is known that EK stack for testing was changed at BEG test-bench between the measurements in 2017 and 2018. On the other side, all of the operating points in the Figure 12 are almost constant during the observed operating periods. As it could be expected, these operating periods (for less than 1 hour each) are definitely too short for the appropriate comparison with the long-term degradation data from the Figure 1, because the stack performance degradation could not be seen in such a short time scale.

3.4 Implementation of the ELFIS diagnostic algorithm

Previously proposed and developed method for single measurement of low frequency impedance intercept using relay excitation scheme was first tested on full stack at EK, and then incorporated in the trailer as a predictive function of the control unit. Figure 13 shows the implemented algorithm for calculation of the low frequency impedance measured by relay excitation.

During the commissioning and trial runs of the trailer, an attempt was made to measure low frequency impedance. Figure 14 shows that it was possible to measure voltage oscillations resulting from relay excitation that was built into the system controller. Unfortunately, it was not possible to properly calculate the impedance because the problems encountered during commissioning and testing of the trailer did not leave enough time to properly calibrate the threshold values of parameters in the impedance calculation algorithm. An additional problem is that it was not possible to isolate the fuel cell stack from other electrical components connected to the same bus, such as the inverter of the compressor's electric motor.

4 Conclusion

The only relevant long-term degradation data is obtained from the tests performed at EK, when the stack was run for 2000 hours. From these results it was possible to extract the degradation rates and then compare them with the degradation rates observed during the accelerated stress tests at FESB reported in deliverable D1.4. This simplified analysis quantifies the time scale of accelerated tests results against long-term degradation data and found that between 0.75 and 1.23 cycles in the accelerated stress test correspond to one hour of stack operating time, depending whether the cell was allowed rejuvenation or not.

Because of unsteady operating conditions and because of the short duration of stacks operation at the test bench and in the trailer, it was not possible to detect any degradation patterns in order to compare them to the results from the accelerated stress tests.

Previously proposed and developed method for single measurement of low frequency impedance intercept was first tested on full stack at EK and then incorporated in the trailer as a predictive function of the control unit. During the commissioning and trial runs of the trailer, an attempt was made to measure low frequency impedance. Unfortunately, it was not possible to properly calculate the impedance because the problems encountered during commissioning and testing of the trailer did not leave enough time to properly calibrate the threshold values of parameters in the impedance calculation algorithm.